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GEORGE EMIL PALADE
UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE,
PHARMACY, SCIENCE, AND
TECHNOLOGY OF TARGU MURES

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Redefining European Security in a Post COVID 19 World

9 May 2023, Targu Mures, Romania

Aula Magna, N. Iorga Street no. 1
Hybrid Format

PROGRAM

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10.00-11.00- Official opening, (Romanian, hybrid form)

Keynote address

Cristian Diaconescu, PhD – Minister of Foreign Affairs, (2008-2009 and 2012), Romanian-American University, Romania

Prof. univ. Radu Carp, PhD – University of Bucharest, Romania

Assoc. prof. Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD, ESDMS Director, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST), Romania

Book Presentation:

Edward N. Luttwak - Ascensiunea Chinei în fața cu logica strategiei, Cuvânt înainte de Radu Carp, Traducere din limba engleză de Radu Carp și Mihai Murariu

11.00-12.30 – Panel 1 – Impact of the pandemic over the international political system

Moderators

Assoc. prof. Gabriela Goudenhoft, PhD, University of Oradea, Romania

Assoc. Prof. Simion Costea, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Panel presentations

Łukasz Perlikowski, PhD, “Central European Countries as a States-System – the Question of International Order’s Stability”, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun, Poland

Assoc. Prof. Simion Costea, PhD, Maria Costea, PhD, “Post-COVID Evolutions in the EU Research Policy”, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania, The Gheorghe Sincai Institute of Social Science and Humanities of the Romanian Academy, Romania

Assoc.prof. Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD, “From Democratic Culture to Security Culture, and Now Resilience. Are They Different in Building Competences to Combat Disinformation?” George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

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Lecturer Cristian Lako, PhD, *“The Post COVID 19 Discourse of the Romanian Presidency”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Lecturer Razvan Paraianu, PhD, *“Plotting the Rebellion: Radical Narratives and the Creation of Fake Realities in an Age of Social Networks”*, Universitatea de Medicină, Farmacie, Științe și Tehnologie George Emil Palade din Targu Mures, Romania

Assoc.prof. Gabriela Goudenhoft, PhD, *“Romania Xenophobia and Alienation. Apprehensions on the Integration of Migrants and Refugees”*, University of Oradea, Romania

Roxana Mihaly, PhD, *“Cultural Diplomacy in the Context of the Digital Transition Caused by the Covid-19 Pandemic”*, The Gheorghe Sincai Institute of Social Science and Humanities of the Romanian Academy, Romania

Assoc.prof Ploșteanu Nicolae, PhD, *“Războiul Mondial al Securității Reci: O Nouă Abordare a Conflictului din Ucraina și Implicațiile pentru Securitatea Uniunii Europene”*, Universitatea de Medicină, Farmacie, Științe și Tehnologie George Emil Palade din Targu Mures, Romania

Panel 2 – EU as a global actor. Global security challenges in the post pandemic international system.

11.00 – 13.00

Zoom link –

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/81292404862?pwd=WFRDd2xBSGtUQ3Z5NDcybDMzMzZmQwZz09>

Meeting ID: 812 9240 4862

Passcode: 877816

Moderators

Leila Nicolas, PhD, Lebanese University, Lebanon

Lecturer Morari Cristina, PhD, Moldova State University

General (r) Marius Craciun, PhD, Universitatea de Medicină, Farmacie, Științe și Tehnologie George Emil Palade din Targu Mures, Romania

Panel presentations

Dr. Lecturer Morari Cristina, *“EU Role in Its Eastern Neighborhood Transformation”*, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova

Lecturer Irina Nicolaescu, *“Solidarity of The International Trade Union Movement in the Post Covid 19 Era”*, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova

Dr. Leila Nicolas, *“How Can the Future of the Middle East Affect European Security?”*, Lebanese University, Lebanon

Alexandru Dorosevici-Duka, *“Information Security in The Republic Of Moldova in The Context of Hybrid Threats”*, Nicolae Testemițanu State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Republic of Moldova

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Lecturer Irina Pop, PhD, *“The Communication Challenges in Defining the Status of the Ukrainian Refugees in Romania of 2023”*, University of Oradea, Romania

Dr Ireneusz Thomas, *“Polish Social Security in the Aftermath of Covid-19”*, MANS Warsaw, Poland

Assoc.Prof. Liubov Melnychuk, PhD *“War in Ukraine: Global Challenges”*, Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine

Assoc.Prof. Md. Shariful Islam, PhD, *“Understanding Bangladesh-EU Relations: From Aid Dependence to Economic Partnership”*, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Asma Ben Jbara, *“Implications of China’s Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) on EU security in a Post COVID 19 World: A Neorealist Framework”*, University of Manouba, Tunisia

Panel 3 – Security challenges in a complex environment: geopolitical, environmental, economic, political

13.00 – 15.00

Zoom link –

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/81292404862?pwd=WFRDd2xBSGtUQ3Z5NDcybDMzMmQwZz09>

Meeting ID: 812 9240 4862

Passcode: 877816

Moderator:

Researcher Daniel-Mihail Sandru, PhD, Center for European Legal Studies, Institute for Legal Research “Andrei Radulescu”, The Romanian Academy

Panel presentations

Stela Spînu, *“The Impact of Ethnocentrism on the Communication of Young People in a Multicultural Environment”*, Nicolae Testemițanu State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Republic of Moldova

Researcher Daniel-Mihail Sandru, PhD, *“Identitatea digitală europeană –politică, tehnologie, drept. În ce ordine?”*, Center for European Legal Studies, Institute for Legal Research “Andrei Radulescu”, The Romanian Academy, Romania

Assoc.prof. Veronica Mocanu, *“Republic of Moldova’s Study Case: Digital Democracy and Digital Repression, Which Path to Follow?”*, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova

Assoc. Prof. Cristina Ejova, PhD, *“Phenomena of Radicalism, Extremism, and Terrorism: Conceptual-Theoretical Landmarks”*, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova

Margareta Beltei, *“Multiculturalism and Political Correctness: Theoretical-Conceptual Aspects”*, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova

Prof. Marieta Safta, PhD, *“Security Challenges from the Perspective of the Constitutional Courts’ Vulnerabilities”*, Titu Maiorescu University Bucharest, Romania

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MSC.Sabina Cenolli and Dr. Zamira Sinaj, *“Measuring Performance Management in Albanian Public Administration”*, University College of Reald, Vlore, Albania "Ismail Qemali" University Vlora, Albania,

Dr. Klajdi Mone *“EU Constitutional Law and the ECHR in the Digital Age: Addressing New Challenges to European Security in the Context of the Pandemic”*, “Ismail Qemali” University Vlora, Albania

Lecturer Armela Maxhelaku, *“Digitalization and Property Rights in Cross-Border Transactions from the Perspective of Private International Law”*, University of Tirana, Albania

Lecturer Ana Buhaljoti, Ph.D and Assoc.Prof. Mirela Mersini, Ph.D, *“Prioritizing Security Awareness in the Fourth Industrial Revolution: Strategies and Considerations”*, University of Tirana, Albania

Daniela Duța, Ph.D, *“Responsible Innovation. Confidentiality, Privacy and Data Protection”* Legal Research Institute of Romanian Academy, Romania

Irina-Cristina Apostolescu, *“Quand le notariat traditionnel rencontre la blockchain, (synthèse documentaire)”*, The National Union of Notaries Public from Romania, Romania

12.30 – 14.00 – Lunch break

Panel 4 - Digital transition & European security

14.00-15.30

Moderators

Lecturer Lucian Sacalean, Ph.D, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Lecturer Adrian Boanta, Ph.D, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Panel presentations

Lecturer Adrian Boanta, Ph.D, *“Digital public administration - a way to engage citizens in a public life”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Lecturer Andreea Ban, Ph.D, *“The Impact of Digital Transition on Education”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Assoc.prof. Raul Felix Hodos, Ph.D, *“Disinformation and Local Public Administration: What, When, and How We Communicate from a Legal Perspective”*, 1 Decembrie 1918 University of Alba Iulia, Romania

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Ruxandra Andreea Lăpădat, *“The Phenomenon of Legal Professions Being Replaced by Artificial Intelligence - Real Danger or Just a Myth?”*, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania

Assoc.prof. Alin Tomus, PhD, *“Politici europene de digitalizare. Cum aducem administrația publică în era digitalizării?”*, 1 Decembrie 1918 University of Alba Iulia, Romania

Lecturer Lucian Sacalean, PhD, *“Threats And Opportunities to European Security - Multi-Ethnic Communities”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

15.30-16.00 - Coffee break

Panel 5 - European security and new challenges

16.00 -17.30

Moderators:

Assoc. Prof. Simion Costea, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Veronica Zaharagiu, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Veronica Zaharagiu, PhD, *“Cultural Diplomacy at War”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Ilie Ceusan *“European Union Policies and Strategies to Tackle Russian Propaganda and Disinformation”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Andrei Guțu, *“Transnistria 2023 – 31 Years of Active Separatism”*, Omega Secondary School, Romania

Assoc. Prof. Simion Costea, PhD, Maria Costea, PhD, *“The EU's Positive Opinion on the Republic of Moldova's Candidate Status (2022)”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania, The Gheorghe Sincai Institute of Social Science and Humanities of the Romanian Academy

Lecturer Raul Miron, PhD, *“Possible Consequences for European Security of the Issuance by the International Criminal Court of the Arrest Warrant for Vladimir Putin”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Natalia Bîrlădeanu, *“UE - R.Moldova, Ucraina, Belarus, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaidjan și Rusia, interesele lor, raporturile de putere și evoluția lor istorică”*, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Dragos Burghilea, Romania - a central pillar of The Three Seas Initiative. Opportunities and challenges, Collegium Intermarium – Varșovia.

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